

DEVELOPMENT OF LOAD TESTING SOFTWARE FOR EOS OPEN STORAGE

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ABSTRACT

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This project focuses on creating a modular load testing and benchmarking tool for testing file systems, specifically EOS storage system. EOS supports storage for data from CERN experiments as well as personal users' data. It relies on protocols like *FUSE* and *XRootD*, which this project aims to test and analyze for any errors or weaknesses. The goal was to create an automated workflow generator and load testing tool, capable of assessing performance, testing the infrastructure and comparing metrics after changing software or hardware configurations.

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1 INTRODUCTION

EOS (EOS Open Storage) is a storage solution for storing large amounts of data from physics experiments and users' files. CERN storage supports petabytes of data being accessed by multiple threads and users simultaneously (Figure 7) [4]. This project aims to emulate user behavior through load testing the development environment of EOS (EOS homedev), while modifying configurations, thereby assessing performance differences and identifying any potential errors during reading and writing data (Figure 1).

To achieve this, a load testing tool was developed, that consists of wrappers around existing benchmarking tools. Furthermore, an analysis script was developed that parses and analyses all output logs from benchmarking tools and prints organized metrics in a comparable and human readable way. This project also explores the behavior of EOS under non-perfect scenarios, by creating pseudo incidents and tampering with software and hardware configurations of EOS instance. Results and analysis of load testing are presented in Chapter 3.

In subsequent chapters of this report we examine some errors and challenges that were encountered and needed to be overcome. We also discuss how the developed tool is scalable, supports future development, and provides reproducible results.

Figure 1: Diagram presenting the objective of this project.

Number of Files 7.87 Bil	Number of Directories 643 Mil	Total Space 774.68 PB	Used Space 532.09 PB	Difference -12.50 PB	Free Space 242.6 PB
Current Writers 8.19 K	Current Readers 46.6 K	IOPS 417K io/s	Write Throughput 28.7 GB/s	Read Throughput 109 GB/s	

Figure 2: EOS statistics collected on 14. 8. 2023 [3].

2 DEVELOPMENT

All software that was developed is located in CERN Gitlab repository [1]. It consists of existing tools' wrappers, centralized configuration file for all the tools, installation script, analysis script, and scripts for docker and continuous deployment of docker images. Repository includes README.md file with code documentation, usage instructions and future development section, making the project easy to use and improve in the future. Architecture of developed software is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Architecture diagram of developed software.

A. TOOLKIT

For benchmarking and load testing purposes, the developed load testing software uses three existing benchmarking tools:

i. Grid Hammer

Grid Hammer is CERN’s internally developed load testing framework designed for use against CERN storage systems, it supports multiple protocols, but in the developed tool we use it to test XRootD protocol [5].

It supports load testing with various operations such as read, write, list, and delete. Users can customize the test by specifying the number of files, threads, and runs.

Optionally, Grid Hammer features an optional visualizer script named "hammer-visualizer" that generates probability distribution of latency for each operation.

ii. Filebench

For testing FUSE protocol, the project uses Filebench, a file system and storage benchmarking software. Filebench supports flexible workloads and allows fine-grained control over operations

and workflows. Through the use of "personalities", users can precisely control each operation and configuration [7, 8].

iii. Fio

As a third tool, we chose Fio I/O tester, which is a well known and developed file system tester. In our case, we utilize it as a micro benchmark to test the FUSE protocol [2].

B. WRAPPERS

To cover a broad spectrum of tests with various parameters, wrappers were created around all the existing benchmarking tools.

Wrappers all work in a similar manner. Initially, they read variables from configuration file, then they create a runspace folder named with the current date for easier server side debugging. Wrappers iterate over all possible parameters defined in configuration file and store logs in a organized fashion. The basic concept is illustrated in code Listing 1.

```
folder=$(date +"%F-%H-%M-%S")
mkdir -p $logs_dir/<tool_name>/$folder
mkdir -p $mountpoint/<tool_name>/$folder

for nthreads in "${num_of_threads[@]}";
do
  for size in "${size_of_file[@]}";
  do
    <tool_name> <flags> | tee <log_folder/nthreads_size.log>
  done
done
```

Listing 1: Wrapper pseudo code.

C. LOADTESTER

The main tool is naively called Loadtester and is another script responsible for executing wrappers, error checking, and running the analysis script, as can be seen from code snippet 2.

All the scripts use centralized configuration file, a normal bash script containing variables for mountpoints, URLs, log directories, and benchmarking parameters.


```
echo -e "Running grid-hammer loadtest...\n"
./tools/hammer-wrapper.sh
if [ ! $? -eq 0 ]; then
    echo -e "ERROR: grid-hammer loadtest was not successful, check logs in
    ↪ $logs_dir\n" >&2
    exit_code=1
fi
```

Listing 2: Code snippet from loadtester.sh.

D. ANALYSIS SCRIPT

The logs generated by benchmarking tools have varying formats and limited readability for programs. To address this, a python program was developed to parse and analyze the logs, presenting the metrics in an readable format and suitable for comparison.

i. Parsing

Parsing of logs depends on benchmarking tool's output. FIO benchmark can output JSON file, so reading metrics was trivial, however Filebench and Grid Hammer outputs had to be parsed manually by string splitting and extracting metrics.

A snippet illustrating the parsing of write throughput from Grid Hammer's output is shown in Listing 3. Importantly, this parsing method is hardcoded and relies on the specific output format, so software versions need to be consistent across installations.

```
elif line.startswith("wr"):
    line = line.split()
    metrics["Write throughput [mb/s]"] = float(line[3].replace("mb/s", ""))
```

Listing 3: Example of analysis script parsing logs.

ii. Comparison

Analysis script is able to read older logs using `-old <n>` flag. This way one can compare side by side two test results using bash command `paste` as show in Listing 4.

```
paste <(/analysis.py --old 2) <(/analysis.py) | column -s $'\t' -t
```

Listing 4: Bash command for side by side comparison of two analysis outputs.

It is possible to use `-compare` flag in the load testing script to automatically compare the last two results. When comparing results, it is important to maintain consistent configurations during runs to ensure that the results are comparable side by side.

iii. Summary

To be able to assess clearly the differences between two test runs, a summary is created at the end of the analysis to put results into context and highlight any significant changes.

For this purpose all the metrics from the analysis script are saved in JSON output format. The summary scripts then reads any two JSON outputs and creates a summary comparison. It presents relative metric improvements in percentages. This script can be ran separately or called by main load testing script if *-compare* flag is passed as an argument. It calculates average relative changes over different parameters for all tests and for important operations. Output of the script is shown in text 5.

Filebench changes:

```
Read throughput: 0.54%
Write throughput: 0.54%
Read latency: 5.56%
Write latency: -4.55%
```

Fio average changes:

```
Read throughput: 0.42%
Write throughput: 0.40%
Read latency: 0.19%
Write latency: 0.55%
```

Hammer average changes:

```
Read rate: 2.49%
Write rate: 2.27%
```

Listing 5: Example of summary.py script output.

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Three scenarios representing different use cases of EOS were created using configuration files to get meaningful and reproducible results. The software then tested the development EOS instance, collecting metrics which are presented in the subsequent sections.

A. PARAMETERS

Parameters were selected to represent different profiles describing usual use cases of users. The first scenario tests single or low-thread operations with a large number of files. Number of files should exceed 30 000 and file size should be under 10 KB.

Next scenario focuses on thread count over 5 and a small number of large files. Around 1 000 to 10 000 files with file size of 1 GB if possible.

The final scenario involves high thread counts, exceeding 10, but with moderate file size and number of files.

However, certain scenarios cannot be fully represented due to limitations of the chosen benchmarking tools.

Users can choose to retain the default parameters, which is a combination of all scenarios or use scenario configuration files, by copying them from the scenario folder. Future users have an ability to change parameters and scenarios easily.

B. METRICS

In Figure 4 we can see the difference in operations rates per second between read, write and delete operations for Grid Hammer benchmarking tool.

Figure 4: Grid Hammer operation rates plotted.

Similarly, the relation between the number of threads and throughput is evident in Figure 5. It should be noted that these relations and metrics significantly depend on various other factors, such as block size and the size of files.

Further manipulation of parameters allows us to achieve a remarkably high throughput with Filebench benchmark testing FUSE protocol (Figure 6). However, it's important to notice

Figure 5: Fio micro benchmark relation between threads and throughput.

Figure 6: High throughput achieved with Filebench benchmark.

that while this level of throughput is attainable, optimizing parameters to achieve the highest metrics may not accurately reflect real-world user scenarios. Such measurements should be used for comparison between multiple runs rather than for making conclusions of EOS performance.

Additional metrics collected by servers can be observed on the Grafana dashboard. After running Loadtester increased network activity can be seen in Figure 7.

Running different scenarios we can observe the relation between size of files and read operation rates (Table 1).

Scenario [reading]	FIO [MiB/s]	Filebench [MB/s]	Hammer [Hz]
Small files	25.3	0.2	1022
Big files	191	519	/
Many threads	1043	760	2038

Table 1: Read performance comparison between scenarios.

Figure 7: Increased network activity observable after running Loadtester.

C. CONFIGURATION CHANGES

During the development of the load testing software, a significant configuration change on EOS software was performed. Previously, EOS stored file consistency metadata (information about files) in levelDB with a transaction for every write operation, which resulted in higher latency. However, after the change, the metadata is now stored as file attributes. This change brings several benefits, such as reducing dependencies on external components and lowering jitter [6]. We were able to detect a substantial increase in write rate performance in XRootD with Grid Hammer benchmark. Although there was notable variation in results during the initial stages of tool development, the performance increase is clearly visible in Figure 8.

Approximate loadtest time: 2023-08-01 13:10:02	Approximate loadtest time: 2023-08-02 08:47:22
===== GRID HAMMER =====	===== GRID HAMMER =====
Number of files 1000	Number of files 1000
Number of threads 10	Number of threads 10
write rate [files/s] 51.95	write rate [files/s] 275.18
write min latency [ms] 40.0	write min latency [ms] 30.0
write max latency [ms] 19230.0	write max latency [ms] 3620.0
read rate [files/s] 1800.3	read rate [files/s] 534.46
read min latency [ms] 30.0	read min latency [ms] 40.0
read max latency [ms] 520.0	read max latency [ms] 1850.0
delete rate [files/s] 954.16	delete rate [files/s] 1036.39
delete min latency [ms] 10.0	delete min latency [ms] 10.0
delete max latency [ms] 1020.0	delete max latency [ms] 940.0
-----	-----
Number of files 1000	Number of files 1000
Number of threads 10	Number of threads 10
write rate [files/s] 86.56	write rate [files/s] 412.06
write min latency [ms] 20.0	write min latency [ms] 30.0
write max latency [ms] 11520.0	write max latency [ms] 2410.0
read rate [files/s] 1497.28	read rate [files/s] 2305.77
read min latency [ms] 50.0	read min latency [ms] 20.0
read max latency [ms] 650.0	read max latency [ms] 390.0
delete rate [files/s] 966.08	delete rate [files/s] 969.36
delete min latency [ms] 10.0	delete min latency [ms] 10.0
delete max latency [ms] 1010.0	delete max latency [ms] 1000.0

Figure 8: Increase in write rate performance above normal variation after configuration change on EOS development machine.

Further similar usage of this tool is expected. However, due to time constraints, we were unable to thoroughly test the tool by emulating incidents or making additional configuration changes on the EOS development machine.

4 ERRORS AND CHALLENGES

A. OPEN FILE LIMIT

During the development of the load testing tool, Grid Hammer encountered two types of errors: a write error labeled as "Numerical argument out of domain" and a read error labeled as "No route to host". These errors appeared at very high thread counts and numbers of files and were consistent. Despite reading client and server logs, we were unable to find a reason or solution for these errors.

After running our software in a Docker container for scalability reasons, no more errors were present. This made it clear that something was different between the testing virtual machine and the Docker container. The main difference was the open files limit, which was confirmed after examining stack traces of programs and checking the software limits with *ulimit -a*. Changing this value from the default Linux value of 1024 to 1048576, which is the default value on most CERN computing machines, fixed the errors.

B. INCONSISTENT TEST RESULTS

The tools used for load testing produced results with substantial variation. Many factors can cause differences in metrics, so trying to find the right parameters and configurations for our software was challenging. This was partially overcome by increasing the testing time, the number of runs, and repeating the full load testing analysis multiple times, as well as running the developed software in containers.

Nevertheless, some of these limitations remain, and small metric changes over consecutive runs are to be expected. For accurate results when changing configurations, users should compare the variation between runs with the same configuration to the variation between runs with different configurations.

C. HIGH NUMBER OF DNS QUERIES

While testing our newly developed software, our team received concerning emails from the DNS team regarding too many DNS requests. Loadtester was creating over 114 requests per second to DNS servers, impacting performance and unintentionally causing a DoS-like attack on the servers. Appropriate measures were taken to ensure DNS caching by enabling *dnsmasq* by our team. Furthermore, the code was inspected to check for any other unintentional performance-degrading calls.

5 SCALABILITY AND AUTOMATION

To ensure a consistent environment, all the software was packaged inside a Docker image using Linux CentOS 7. The Dockerfile installs all the necessary dependencies and prepares the environment for testing. In order to make further development easier, creating docker images was automated by using automatic Gitlab's CI/CD tools, which build docker image from repository a commit is made to the main branch, as presented in Listing 6.

Furthermore, all the software is written in a modular way, with additional development instructions added to the documentation to support future developers in adding new tools to the Loadtester.

Future users can scale up the testing of EOS by utilizing multiple virtual machines with running containers to emulate workflows resembling users' behavior.

```
build_docker_image:
  stage: build
  variables:
    IMAGE_DESTINATION: "${CI_REGISTRY_IMAGE}:latest"
  image:
    name: gcr.io/kaniko-project/executor:debug
    entrypoint:
      - ''
  script:
    - echo "{\"auths\":{\"${CI_REGISTRY}\":
{\"username\": \"${CI_REGISTRY_USER}\", \"password\": \"${CI_REGISTRY_PASSWORD}\"}}}"
↪ > /kaniko/.docker/config.json
    - "/kaniko/executor --context $CI_PROJECT_DIR --dockerfile
↪ $CI_PROJECT_DIR/Dockerfile
      --destination $IMAGE_DESTINATION"
  only:
    - master
```

Listing 6: gitlab-ci.yml file

6 FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

Since the project did not have a singular, specific goal, there is room for further work and improvements. Apart from testing the software and using it as intended, developers can add more benchmarking tools and scripts to extend the capabilities of Loadtester.

A. SCENARIOS AND CONFIGURATIONS

More research should be invested in searching for good configurations and scenarios that represent usual users' behavior. The parameters used for scenarios should be justified. Configurations should be chosen so that the load test doesn't necessarily present the best possible metrics but rather results similar to real-world use cases.

B. UNUSUAL BEHAVIOR

During the last weeks of development, some occasional failures were found. Grid Hammer reports a *No route to host* error, even after increasing the open files limit. This did not happen before and should be investigated.

Filebench occasionally fails on certain workflows. It's very likely that this is a problem with workflow definitions (Filebench personalities) or a Filebench bug.

When the Grid Hammer benchmark reports poor metrics, it is usually due to a few latency outliers (a few operations taking seconds to complete) rather than decreased performance throughout the entire run. It might be interesting to explore the reason for these extreme latency outliers in verbose grid hammer logs and server logs.

C. EXPORTING METRICS

Some suggestions were made to export the data collected by the developed load testing tool to a Grafana dashboard. Parsed data is currently saved in JSON format after running the analysis script. Perhaps in a similar way, data could be sent to the dashboard every time the analysis script is called. Testing and displaying useful data on the dashboard could be automated every few hours.

7 CONCLUSION

The development of a load testing and benchmarking tool for testing EOS Open Storage has been successfully accomplished in this project. The main objectives were met, resulting in a functional tool that automates load testing, assesses performance, tests infrastructure, and performs the comparison of metrics under configuration changes.

The developed tool was already proven useful in detecting improvements after configuration changes on EOS. Further similar use of this tool is expected to detect any changes in performance while changing configurations or emulating pseudo incidents on the EOS development server.

The project also encountered and addressed various challenges, such as Linux open file limit issues, inconsistent test results, and excessive DNS queries. These challenges were tackled through troubleshooting, debugging, and fine-tuning of parameters.

The developed tool is made scalable and supports further development through its integration with Docker containers and the utilization of GitLab's CI/CD tools. This ensures a consistent testing environment and supports future changes to the code.

Furthermore, the developed software still has room for improvements. Certain challenges were not fully overcome, and some unusual behavior still needs to be investigated. More research needs to be done on scenarios and configurations to ensure they represent usual user behavior. The project can be further improved by adding new tools or scripts either for load testing or displaying metrics.

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